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A PERSPECTIVE OF GLOBAL

**SCENARIO AND FUTURE
CHALLENGES IN WORLD IN
THE 21ST CENTURY**

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the State also another means to the same end has been the trade agreement of the Centre with foreign States, with no reference made to States whose products thereby may be priced out of the market. Demonetization in 2016 was also taken by the Centre without any reference to the State impacted drastic on employment and cooperative sector in the State. The present research article focus on the challenges in the Centre-State relations.

PATHWAY TOWARDS AGRICULTURAL GLOBALIZATION IN INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

Globalization is the process of increasing connectivity and interdependence of the world's markets and businesses. The theory behind globalization is that worldwide openness will promote the inherent wealth of all nations. Globalization refers to the integration of economies and societies all over the world. As economies become more connected to other economies, they have increased opportunity but also increased competition. Pro-globalization lobby argues that globalization brings about increased opportunities for almost everyone. Multinational companies are able to increase their production and profits because they have already penetrated the local markets. Globalization has a lot to do with the rise of multinational corporations, according to researchers at the University of Michigan's Wharton School of Business in the United States. The World Trade Organization (WTO), International Monetary Fund (IMF), and World Bank (WB) are important global actors. Globalization has led to greater influence of NGOs in areas of great concern like human rights, the environment, children, and workers. The World Trade Organization (WTO) was established in 1995. Its primary purpose is to open trade for the benefit of all. Decisions in the WTO are generally taken by consensus of the entire membership. The organization has 155 members, of which 117 are developing countries or separate customs territories. The World Trade Organization's (WTO) main activities include. Negotiating the reduction or elimination of obstacles to trade (e.g. import tariffs, other barriers to trade) and agreeing on rules governing the conduct of international trade. The organisation's founding and guiding principles remain the pursuit of open borders. The General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) was signed in 1947. GATT was replaced by the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995. There

are currently 155 member countries in the WTO, with Montenegro and Samoa being new members as of 2012. GATT was a set of rules agreed upon by nations, the WTO is an institutional body. Serbia and Montenegro are expected to join the WTO in 2012 or 2013. After LPG the agro-allied industries created employment in various sector like packing, exporting, standardizing, processing, transportation and cold storage. Use of modern agro technologies in pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizers as well as new breeds of high yield crops were employed to increase food production. Agriculture accounts for 10.23% of India's export income but imports account for just 2.74%. Globalization has led to a vicious debt trap and increase in farmers suicides, says World Bank economist Jagmohan Ramachandra Sekaran. Nobel Laureates' research has already helped to alleviate global poverty. It has great potential to further improve the lives of the worst of people, say Oxfam's leaders. Abhijit Banerjee, Michael Kremer and Coats van der Voortrekker are this year's winners.

Keywords: Globalisation; agriculture; Indian economy; history

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract

Globalization has altered the way we live and earn a livelihood. Consequently, trade and travel have been recognized as significant determinants of the spread of disease. Additionally, the rise in urbanization and the closer integration of the world economy have facilitated global interconnectedness. Therefore, globalization has emerged as an essential mechanism of disease transmission. This paper aims to examine the potential impact of COVID-19 on globalization and global health in terms of mobility, trade, travel, and countries most impacted.

The effects of globalization were operationalized in terms of mobility, economy, and healthcare systems. The mobility of individuals and its magnitude was assessed using airline and seaport trade data and travel information. The economic impact was measured based on the workforce, event cancellations, food and agriculture, academic institutions, and supply chain. The healthcare capacity was assessed by considering healthcare system indicators and